

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CHECKING WRITTEN HOMEWORK IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In the Russian and foreign methods, there are different approaches to verification of written work in a foreign language depending on the fact that it checks the teacher. It is logical to assume that a continuous check of various tasks, including training exercises, the purpose of which is to master new grammatical material, which consists in repeatedly prescribing the same phenomenon according to the model, consumes a huge amount of time and is absolutely ineffective.

Foreign language training in teaching students involves, among other things, the formation of writing skills, as well as widespread use as compared with subspecialties written independent work and home. The rather clearly prescribed types of teaching load of the teacher do not allow him to spend an unlimited amount of time on checking written assignments, especially since this is ineffective from the point of view of the educational process. The teacher is faced with a dilemma of how to reduce the time for checking, while paying maximum attention to the written work of students.

The scope of this report does not allow to fully consider all types and methods of checking written works in a foreign language, but the following should be considered the main ones:

1. Correction of every mistake made in the text of the work.

This is exactly what most students want, but one must be aware of the possible negative psychological impact of this huge

mass of red paste corrections. It may be better to use this method to check especially important parts of the work, or sometimes it is better to selectively pay attention only to basic errors. In addition, the question arises about how students are able to work through all the numerous errors on their own. Even when working on mistakes, students, firstly, cannot always arrive at the correct version without the help of a teacher, and secondly, if there are many mistakes, students are psychologically and even physically unable to analyze and, therefore, correct all mistakes. That is why solid error checking in most cases is not only redundant, but also harmful.

Indeed, in our opinion, it is necessary to correct all errors in the texts that determine the level of students, possibly in creative works (essays, essays, articles, etc.).

2. The list of errors and comments on a separate sheet of paper is a variation on the previous method.

Indicate each error in the margin (in an essay), then use the same icons to mark the errors on a separate sheet of paper and write your comments. Attach the sheet to the work so that students can read and analyze the errors point by point. This method increases the responsibility of students for further work on their mistakes, since the teacher's comments are perceived as a personal letter and, therefore, there is a direct communication between the teacher and the student.

3. Correction of previously agreed errors only.

For example, the teacher corrects only grammatical errors passed during the last lessons or all errors in one paragraph so that the student can correctly assess their knowledge and work through the material more thoroughly before submitting the next work. In our opinion, this is one of the most effective verification methods. By correcting errors for active grammar or vocabulary, the teacher can be sure that students have at their disposal learning materials that will effectively correct all marked errors.

4. Students themselves can propose a way to test.

At the very beginning of the work, students indicate how they want to be checked, for example - all grammatical errors. However, you should not always follow their lead and check all the mistakes. The check can be carried out orally, in the form of a dialogue with students. In turn, the teacher can offer students the most rational, from their point of view, methods of checking their choice. It makes sense to explain to students in advance what and how the teacher checks.

5. Underlining errors.

For example, choose a symbol - a line and a circle, for example, it will be a cross in the margins where a mistake was made, but

not a correction or an underline of the mistake itself. This method will help motivate students to devote more time to proven work and try to learn more about their mistakes and opportunities to correct them. This method is especially effective when checking tasks for opening parentheses, inserting prepositions, prescribing by models.

6. Pointing some anonymous bugs on the board.

Either in a group or in pairs, students find mistakes and correct them. When the check is over, students can look at their work and mistakes. Estimates can be announced after checking incorrectly composed proposals. In our opinion, with any method of checking, the teacher must draw the students' attention to typical mass mistakes.

7. Self-correction of errors by students using the keys.

To prevent the teacher from being the only source of knowledge, students can be provided with keys and answers from the teacher's file so that they themselves can correct their mistakes, and the teacher can then help with those errors.

8. Work in groups, in pairs.

Students need to be reminded that whenever they write something, they can let a friend read it first. Once they get used to doing this, they will have knowledge gleaned from other people's mistakes, and this will also improve their understanding of their common mistakes.

9. Return to previously checked works.

Ask students to go back to previously written papers and look for 3 positions where their English has improved and 2 where they can still improve in order to see an improvement in their skills. Together with this, the teacher can scan and store the best copies of previously well-written works and use them in the educational process so that students can see the goal that needs to be

achieved or even surpassed. Such a bank of works is also needed as samples (for example, essays).

Pedagogical experience and specific tasks can help the teacher choose the most effective test method. In our opinion, the

main thing is that the student is aware of the need to work on his mistakes, and the student's motivation does not decrease after receiving a proven work, containing even numerous mistakes.

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